

DEPARTMENT OF AYURVEDA
MINISTRY OF HEALTH
SRI LANKA

UNIVERSITY OF
KELANIYA | Faculty of
Graduate Studies

2nd International Research Symposium on Traditional Medicine

“**One Health for Sustainable and Healthy Living of
Humans, Animals, and Ecosystems**”

Organized by

The Faculty of Graduate Studies, University of Kelaniya

In collaboration with

The Department of Ayurveda, Ministry of Health, Sri Lanka

ABSTRACTS

DEPARTMENT OF AYURVEDA
MINISTRY OF HEALTH
SRI LANKA

UNIVERSITY OF
KELANIYA | Faculty of
Graduate Studies

2nd International Research Symposium on Traditional Medicine (AyurEx Colombo) – 2024

Proceedings of the 2nd Symposium

**“One health for sustainable and healthy living of
humans, animals, and ecosystems”**

Abstracts

3rd – 5th May 2024

**The Faculty of Graduate Studies, University of Kelaniya,
Sri Lanka
in collaboration with
The Department of Ayurveda, Ministry of Health, Sri Lanka**

Development of sprouted sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) flour incorporated biscuits

J. Mathumitha^{1*}, H. K. P. P. Kariyawasam¹, and K. G. S. J. Madushanka¹

¹Department of Agricultural Technology, Faculty of Technology, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka

Biscuits stand out as the leading category of snack worldwide due to the taste, ease of handling and long shelf-life though it is regarded unhealthy. Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) is the fifth major cereal crop in terms of worldwide production and bears a range of health benefits. Sprouting is a cost-effective approach for enhancing the nutritional content and functional properties of grains. This study attempted at developing sprouted sorghum flour incorporated biscuits. The biscuits were prepared by adding different proportions (0, 30, 40 & 50 %) of sprouted sorghum flour (SSF) with wheat flour. In terms of sensory attributes, the biscuit made with 30 % sprouted sorghum flour biscuit (SSFIB) showed best acceptance; in terms of color (6.46±0.29), appearance (6.69±0.26), texture (6.53±0.46), aroma (6.46±0.29), taste (7.30±0.32), mouthfeel (7.07±0.44) and overall acceptability (7.23±0.39). The proximate composition of 30 % SSF incorporated biscuits was found to contain approximately 357 kcal energy, 66 g carbohydrate, 5 g fat, 13 g protein, 15 g fiber, 2 g ash, 13 g sugar, 0.73 g salt per 100 g and 2.49 % (wb) moisture. The functional properties of 30% SSF incorporated biscuits were as follows; swelling capacity 7.3±0.04 ml, water absorption capacity 2.63±0.03 g/g, bulk density 0.36±0.02 g/cm³, true density 0.66±0.02 g/cm³ and spread ratio 1.6±0.20. The market survey indicated strong consumer acceptance with the majority favoring the taste, aroma, and appearance, resulting in a positive overall preference. Therefore, this study highlights that 30 % SSF incorporated biscuits offer a nutritious and well-received alternative in the market while promoting the use of sorghum in bakery products.

Keywords: Biscuit, Functional properties, Proximate composition, Sprouted sorghum flour

*m.jeya568@gmail.com